

CERTIFICATE

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

N.O.Akhmedov

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALIDA

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS IN ENGINEERING SCIENCES AND COMPUTER GRAPHICS

DISCIPLINES BASED ON A PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACH

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